

which was susceptible to gall midge and other pests, in station trials (1981-82) and minikit trials (1988-91) at different sites in Telangana zone.

Erra Mallelu had no or negligible incidence of galls compared with checks Jaya and TN1 in trials at numerous locations. The variety is now grown on 50,000 ha in the zone.

Kavya (WGL48684) is a medium-duration variety (see table) that is similar in grain type but 10 d earlier than the locally popular Samba Mahsuri, which is susceptible to gall midge and other pests. Kavya showed no or negligible incidence of galls in many trials at several locations from 1987 to 1989. Its yield performance in multi-

location and national trials from 1987 to 1989 was promising. Kavya is grown on 40,000 ha.

Orugallu (WGL47970) is a long-duration, high-yielding (4.7 t ha⁻¹) rice variety (see table). It performs well in slightly saline soils and was resistant to gall midge in the 1987-89 trials. It is grown on 20,000 ha. ■

Stress tolerance—other stresses

Flowering behavior of rainfed lowland rice varieties during dry season in West Bengal, India

S. K. Sinha and S. D. Chatterjee, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal 712102, India

We studied the flowering behavior of five popular rainfed lowland rice cultivars (CN540, CNM539, Mahsuri, Pankaj, and IR42) compared with that of two photoperiod-insensitive boro checks (Jaya and IR26).

Seeds were sown on three dates during 1992-93 and 1993-94 dry seasons. Rice is traditionally sown in June-July and harvested in November-December in West Bengal. Daylength peaks in July (13 h 11 min) (Table 1).

Low temperature from November to January limits seedling growth, which extends crop duration. Early- to medium-duration photoperiod-

Table 1. Mean daylength and minimum and maximum temperature of each month. Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India.

Month	Day length		Minimum temperature (°C)	Maximum temperature (°C)
	H	Min		
January	10	43	10.2	25.6
February	11	14	13.2	28.7
March	11	51	18.5	33.7
April	12	22	22.9	36.8
May	13	06	25.0	36.4
June	13	24	25.5	33.9
July	13	11	25.7	31.7
August	12	50	25.7	31.3
September	12	11	25.5	31.5
October	11	31	22.9	31.0
November	10	55	16.0	28.8
December	10	36	10.0	25.6

insensitive modern boro varieties are popular in this season. We studied the performance of longer duration rainfed lowland rice varieties under these conditions, which had not been done to date.

Seeds were sown on 23 Nov, 12 Dec, and 28 Jan and transplanted on 10 Jan, 8 Feb, and 3 Mar, respectively, for two

consecutive dry seasons (1992-93 and 1993-94), with three replications for each sowing.

The data were recorded for initial flowering (first panicle in the plot), 50% flowering (half of the panicle in the plot), 100% flowering (every panicle in the plot), and grain yield (t ha⁻¹) pooled over 2 yr (Table 2).

Table 2. Flowering behavior and grain yield of different lowland rice varieties under different sowing dates in West Bengal, India. 1992-94^a.

Variety	Sowing date									Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	23 Nov			12 Dec			28 Jan					
	Days to flowering			Days to flowering			Days to flowering			23 Nov	12 Dec	28 Jan
	Initial	50%	100%	Initial	50%	100%	Initial	50%	100%			
Pankaj	140	144	147	130	136	140	145	152	162	5.3	4.4	3.8
IR42	135	140	144	120	125	129	105	108	110	5.4	4.8	4.2
CN540	147	160	167	130	155	169	150	162	175	4.7	3.0	2.5
CNM539	139	143	145	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.8		
Mahsuri	147	154	158	135	139	143	137	145	152	4.5	3.7	3.3
Jaya	135	140	145	123	127	131	102	105	108	5.6	5.1	4.4
IR36	127	130	135	116	122	127	94	98	103	5.3	5.0	4.2
CD (variety × sowing date) at 0.05 level	8	4	4	8	4	4	8	4	4	0.6	0.6	0.6

^aData pooled over 1992-93 and 1993-94.

For the November planting, the varieties were generally consistent in duration between initial and 100% flowering, regardless of the magnitude of photoperiod sensitivity (Table 2). The exception was CN540, which took as long as 20 d to finish flowering. Lowland varieties sown after November, however, had different flowering patterns and the variety \times sowing date interaction was significant for duration to initial flowering, 50% flowering, and 100% flowering. CNM539 did not flower at all.

While time to flowering gradually decreased for IR42, Jaya, and IR36 in successive sowings, duration of Pankaj, CN540, and Mahsuri decreased from November to December but increased again in January. Though all other varieties flowered, none, except IR72, retained their flowering synchrony (a short interval between initial and 100% flowering) that simplifies harvesting. IR42 appeared to be the best variety with synchronous flowering behavior under all the sowing dates.

Flowering during mid- to late June for varieties such as Pankaj, Mahsuri, and CN540 is not conducive for higher grain yield. Long vegetative growth exposes the crop to the beginning of the southwest monsoon, often leading to lodging followed by seed sprouting. A good harvest with these varieties cannot be assured. On the other hand, the earliest variety, IR42, yielded comparably with Jaya and IR36. The advantage of IR42 is its long slender grain, which receives a premium in the market. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Vijetha: a high-yielding, short-duration rice variety for Andhra Pradesh, India

Y. Suryanarayana, P. Sankara Rao, N. Sree Rama Reddi, K. R. K. Murthy, and P. S. S. Murty, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Maruteru 534122, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Vijetha was developed from a cross between MTU5249 and MTU7014, using the pedigree breeding method at ARS.

Vijetha was highly promising in research station trials conducted during the 1991-94 dry seasons (Table 1). It yielded a mean 7.5 t ha⁻¹ and consistently produced at least 1 t ha⁻¹ more than check IR64—an average yield advantage of 22.8%.

In the All India Coordinated Trials during 1993 dry season, Vijetha re-

corded a mean yield of 4.9 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2) across 15 locations, indicating its wide adaptability.

At Maruteru, we used the seedbox technique to determine that the variety is resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), scoring a 3 on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale. Vijetha is also moderately resistant to gall midge (biotype 1), BPH, whitebacked planthopper, stem borer, leafroller, and blast.

Vijetha is a semidwarf (105 cm) with dark green foliage and a broad, erect flag leaf. It possesses 8-10 productive tillers plant⁻¹. Flowering is completed in 3-4 d, contributing to uniform maturity. The panicle length is 26 cm and grains panicle⁻¹ total about 150; 1,000-grain weight is 24 g. The grain is medium-shaped and translucent, with a length-breadth ratio of 2.6 (length is 6.2 cm, breadth 2.4 cm). Dormancy ranges from 6 to 8 wk during kharif (dry

season). Milling percentage is 65.8%, with a 62.4% head rice recovery, and 5.0% broken rice percentage, classifying it as a fine-grained rice.

Results from 530 minikit trials conducted during 1994 and 1995 confirmed the superiority of Vijetha over check IR64 across Andhra Pradesh. Vijetha can be grown in either the wet season (145 d) or dry season (125 d).

It is a nonlodging, fertilizer responsive variety with resistance to several pests. Even before 3yr of minikit testing was completed, Vijetha was planted on more than 150,000 ha in Andhra Pradesh. Because of its outstanding potential, the State Seed Subcommittee released Vijetha in 1995. ■

Table 1. Yield performance of Vijetha at Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, India. 1991-94 dry seasons.

Year	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		% increase over IR64	CV (%)	LSD (5%)
	Vijetha	IR64			
1991	7.5	5.6	33.9	11.3	0.9
1992	7.9	6.6	19.7	7.2	0.7
1993	7.7	6.2	24.2	13.0	1.0
1994	6.8	6.0	13.3	7.5	0.6
Mean	7.5	6.1	22.8		

Table 2. Performance of Vijetha at different locations in India. 1993 kharif.

State	Locations (no.)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a	
		Vijetha	Ratna (check)
Kerala	3	5.6	2.9
Tamil Nadu	3	6.5	4.8
Karnataka	2	4.8	5.4
Andhra Pradesh	3	4.6	4.6
Gujarat	1	3.5	0.8
Haryana	1	4.9	3.8
Uttar Pradesh	2	2.2	3.4
Mean ^b		4.9	4.0

^aMean of the locations in the state. ^bMean of 15 locations.